

SCIENTIFIC, AND PRACTICAL SPECIFIC FEATURES OF DEVELOPING RECREATIONAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN.

Po'latova Mavluda Sanjar qizi

Doctoral Student (3rd year)

Department of Tourism and Hotel Business

Tashkent State University of Economics

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается комплексная оценка развития рекреационного туризма с акцентом на выявление взаимодействия структурных элементов туристической инфраструктуры и макроэкономических факторов. В частности, в качестве основных детерминантов спроса на туристические услуги рассматриваются такие факторы, как транспортная инфраструктура, цифровые информационные системы, состояние окружающей среды и уровень доходов населения. Статья посвящена вопросам того, как эти факторы в своей взаимной интеграции определяют эффективность туристической системы и формируют динамику ее развития.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, рекреационный туризм, устойчивое развитие, современная экономика, транспортная инфраструктура, цифровая информация, состояние окружающей среды, факторы доходов населения, методологическая основа, эконометрическое моделирование, модель ARDL, интеграция, организационно-экономический механизм.

Abstract: This article focuses on the complex assessment of the development of recreational tourism, focusing on identifying the interaction of structural elements of tourism infrastructure and macroeconomic factors. In particular, factors such as transport infrastructure, digital information systems, environmental status and population income are considered as the main determinants of the demand for tourism services. The article is devoted to the issues of how these factors, in their mutual integration, determine the effectiveness of the tourism system and shape the dynamics of its development.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, recreational tourism, sustainable development, modern economy, transport infrastructure, digital information, environmental status, population income factors, methodological framework, econometric modeling, ARDL model, integration, organizational and economic mechanism.

The issue of sustainable development of recreational tourism in Uzbekistan requires a multifactorial and systematic approach in modern economic conditions.

Recreational tourism is not only a set of services related to recreation and health, but also a complex system that is closely related to the economy, transport, service provision, digital technologies, ecology and the well-being of the population. Therefore, the use of modern econometric modeling approaches, along with traditional statistical analysis methods, is of great importance in the scientific assessment of this area.

In a comprehensive assessment of the development of recreational tourism, the main attention is paid to identifying the interaction of structural elements of tourism infrastructure and macroeconomic factors. In particular, factors such as transport infrastructure, digital information systems, environmental status and population income are considered the main determinants of the and shape the dynamics of its development.

The methodological basis of the study is formed by two important areas of econometric modeling. First, the ARDL model based on time series is used to determine the dynamic relationship between elements of recreational tourism infrastructure and international tourist flows. This approach allows for a joint assessment of short-term fluctuations and long-term equilibrium relationships between variables. Second, the multivariate linear regression (LS) model is used to identify the main macroeconomic factors affecting the volume of tourism services, and the impact of transport, digitalization, ecology and income factors is assessed in a comprehensive manner. The joint use of these two approaches provides a significant scientific advantage in assessing recreational tourism. While the ARDL model allows for the identification of the time-lagged impact of tourism infrastructure, the LS regression model serves to identify the interrelationships of the main economic factors affecting the volume of tourism services. As a result, tourism development is comprehensively analyzed in relation not only to infrastructure factors, but also to the macroeconomic environment.

As part of the study, an integrated organizational and economic mechanism was proposed to ensure the sustainable development of recreational tourism in Uzbekistan. This mechanism is based on the interrelated consideration of infrastructure factors, macroeconomic determinants and management tools affecting the tourism sector within a single system.

As the first component, macroeconomic factors are of particular importance. The level of income of the population, the development of digital technologies (level of Internet use) and the environmental situation are the main factors shaping the overall demand for tourism services. While an increase in income expands the population's opportunities to use tourist services, digitalization processes ensure the convenience

and openness of tourism services. Ecological factors are considered an important factor determining the attractiveness of recreational areas. As a result, under the influence of these factors, the initial demand for tourism is formed.

The second component is the infrastructure block, which is the main mechanism that converts the formed demand into a real tourism flow. This block includes transport infrastructure, cultural tourism facilities and recreational facilities. While transport infrastructure ensures the accessibility of tourists to the regions, cultural and recreational facilities form the main content of the tourist product. The results of econometric analysis also confirm that it is these factors that have the most significant impact on tourism flows. Therefore, the infrastructure block is considered a “practical driver” of tourism development.

The third component is an organizational mechanism that ensures the effective functioning of the entire system. Within this mechanism, public-private partnerships (PPP), tourism clusters and cooperative relations are considered the main tools. These management instruments serve to develop infrastructure facilities, attract investment flows and strengthen cooperation between tourism entities. As a result, the institutional efficiency of the tourism system increases.

An important aspect of the proposed mechanism is that all components are interconnected and work as a single system. In particular, the demand formed through macroeconomic factors is transformed into a real tourism flow through the infrastructure, and the organizational mechanism coordinates and supports this process. At the same time, an increase in tourism flows can have a positive effect on economic growth and create new demand in the future. This indicates the presence of a dynamic and self-stimulating mechanism in the system.

The proposed integrated organizational and economic mechanism provides a comprehensive approach to the development of recreational tourism and allows achieving sustainable development based on the integration of infrastructure, economic factors and the management system. This model is of scientific and practical importance in the strategic development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and serves as an important methodological basis for improving tourism policy.

The organizational mechanism acts as a “coordinating institution” in the economic system. It manages the flow of investment, ensures the efficient use of resources and strengthens ties between tourism entities. As a result, the development of infrastructure accelerates and the flow of tourism steadily increases.

The integrated working mechanism of the model The main logical chain of this model is expressed as follows:

Macroeconomic factors → Demand formation → Infrastructure → Tourism flow.

At the same time:

✓ Organizational mechanism → Infrastructure → Tourism flow

This indicates the two-way operation of the model:

➤ top-down (demand → supply)

➤ bottom-up (management → development)

The most powerful aspect of the dynamic effect (self-developing system) model is its dynamic nature. An increase in tourism flow increases economic activity, which in the future leads to an increase in income and the formation of new demand.

As a result, the following closed cycle occurs:

✓ Tourism flow ↑ → Income ↑ → Demand ↑ → Infrastructure ↑ → Tourism

This is also confirmed by the inertia (lag) effect identified in the econometric model. That is, the development of tourism in the previous period also has a positive effect on the next period. This means that the system has a self-stimulating and sustainable development.

The database consists of indicators and outcome variables representing the main structural elements of the recreational tourism infrastructure, which are systematized as follows:

➤ (Number of international tourists) - a dependent variable, representing the flow of international tourists entering the country and is considered the main indicator of the development of recreational tourism.

➤ (Accommodation infrastructure) - reflects the number of hotels, guest houses and other accommodation facilities.

➤ (Information infrastructure) - reflects the development of Wi-Fi points, information centers and digital services.

➤ (Transport infrastructure) - characterizes the availability of tourist vehicles and interregional mobility.

➤ (Catering infrastructure) - includes the number of restaurants, cafes and other catering facilities.

➤ (Cultural tourism infrastructure) – reflects theaters, cultural heritage sites, folklore and handicraft activities.

➤ (Recreational tourism infrastructure) – represents recreation areas, ecotourism and wellness facilities.

These variables were selected as the main economic and institutional factors affecting tourism flows, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of recreational tourism infrastructure.

General description of data dynamics Analysis of the data in the table shows that during the study period, a positive growth trend was observed for almost all indicators. In particular, the number of international tourists (Number of International Tourists) increased over time, and although there was a sharp decrease in some periods (the pandemic period in 2020), rapid recovery and growth dynamics were noted in recent years.

Infrastructure indicators also increased significantly. In particular, the annual increase in the number of accommodation infrastructure (Accommodation Infrastructure), information infrastructure (Information Infrastructure), and cultural and recreational facilities indicates an increase in the volume of investments in the tourism sector. In particular, the rapid development of transport infrastructure (Transport Infrastructure) and information infrastructure (Food Infrastructure) has significantly expanded the convenience and accessibility of tourism services.

The use of this database in econometric analysis allows the use of modern econometric modeling methods in assessing the development of recreational tourism. In particular, based on this data, which has a time series nature:

- The dynamics of variables over time is analyzed;
- Seasonality and cyclical fluctuations are identified;
- The short- and long-term relationship between infrastructure factors and tourism flows is assessed.

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